

CLEWs Modeling for Algeria: Assessing Energy Expansion, Food Security, and Water Desalination Strategies by 2050

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This study explores Algeria's long-term development pathways between 2024 to 2050 across land-use, energy, and water systems using OSeMOSYS tool and CLEWs farmwork modelling. The analysis assesses multiple national strategies, including renewable energy expansion, crop self-sufficiency, and water desalination, under varying electricity demand growth scenarios.

The results shows that natural gas remains the main energy source for electricity generation across all scenarios, with a modest renewable penetration unless supported by structural reforms. The National Renewable Energy Program, which adds 15 GW of solar and wind by 2035, contributes just 5% to the electricity mix by 2050 in the base line scenario, though it effectively reduces both CO₂ emissions and water consumption comparing to other scenarios. In high-demand scenarios, nuclear power emerges as a stabilizing baseload to mitigate curtailment and maintain grid reliability.

In the food and land sectors, achieving full domestic crop production by 2030, especially for wheat and barley, requires extensive land allocation and places additional pressure on water resources. While precipitation becomes the primary water source for crops, limited irrigation capacity constrains agricultural expansion. To address this, the model reallocates some irrigated land to rainfed systems, increasing vulnerability to climate variability. Improved yields through climate-resilient crop varieties are essential to avoid unsustainable land and water expansion.

The 100% local crop scenario significantly reduces imports and emissions but incurs the highest total system cost, whereas the National Renewable Energy Program offers a more balanced solution with lower environmental and financial trade-offs. The analysis highlights that land–water–energy interdependencies must be addressed through integrated, cross-sectoral planning to ensure a sustainable and resilient future for Algeria.

1. Introduction:

Climate Change, Energy, Water and Food are the fundamental pillars around which the Sustainable Goals are based (UN DESA, 2020). Climate Change is one of the most debated topics, attracting global attention and common responsibility. Human activity over the last century has widely contributed to the emergence of this phenomenon through GHG emissions generated from the excess use of fossil fuels. These emissions have unequivocally caused the warming of the climate system, with global surface temperature reaching 1.1°C above 1850–1900 in 2011–2020 (IPCC, 2023).

Algeria is considered one of the most important players in the energy sector, especially in the Mediterranean basin, as it effectively produces and supplies some Mediterranean countries with energy. According to (World Energy data, 2023). A sustainable energy transition roadmap is a common responsibility and a necessity toward the ambitious 1.5 threshold, means every share will bring us closer to the goal. The increase need for resources and exerts demand on land and water systems as natural result of population growth which leads to the emergence of serious difficulties in resources management, furthermore.

The water available per capita in Algeria was 956 m³/capita in 1962, whilst 246 m³/capita in 2021, the World bank theoretical threshold is 1000 m³/capita (Touitou & Al-Aminb, 2020), the water scarcity and inefficient water consumption witnessed in the region is a wicked problem that going to be worse, due to the demographic growth, climate change and Socio-economic development (de Waal, Khemani, Barone, & Borgomeo, 2023), which requires a sophisticated resources management system.

The food security is not isolated from the previous context that Algeria is experiencing, 81.5% of the Algeria land is non-Agriculture productive land, and only 18.5% of it is useful agricultural land (Bertini & Zouache, 2021). Open-Source energy MOdelling SYStem (OSeMOSYS) considered as long-term energy planning framework, bottom-up, technology-detailed, and linear programming model (Gardumi et al., 2018), besides the it's a diverse applications for modeling the different energy planning narratives, such the decarbonization pathways (Aboumahboub et al., 2020; Godínez-Zamora et al., 2020; Jaggeshar et al., 2025), power sector Capacity analysis (Groissböck & Pickl, 2018; Paiboonsin et al., 2024), Transport sector(Keller et al., 2019; Taliotis et al., 2020) , Regional grographical Analysis (Dallmann, Schmidt, & Möst, 2022; Santos, 2021; Taliotis, Karmellos, Fylaktos, & Zachariadis, 2023), the OSeMOSYS can be also used to model and interlink Climate, Land-Use (Food), Energy and Water Systems (Almulla et al., 2018;Alexander, K et al., 2025; Kuling, Barnes, Shivakumar, Brinkerink, & Niet, 2022).

This Report's main aim is to develop an integral Climate, Land-use, Energy, and waters System model, which provides policy-relevant economics and investigates the interconnectedness between different sectors and the use of global resources. This initiative will enhance Algeria's capacity to formulate data-driven policies that optimize the synergies between energy, water, and land use, fostering, sustainable economic growth and environmental stewardship with least-cost.

2. Methodology:

The methodology mainly based on the CLEWs six stages model development provided by (Martindale et al., 2023), in which the stages starts with Narrative formulation, than identify the relevant data and indicators, the third step is the model structure development, model calibration, the next stage in this framework is to designing the scenarios to be analysed, the sixth step Analyse the findings and formulate the policy recommendations.

This study relies on the OSeMOSYS framework, to assess long-term resource planning within an integrated Climate, Land, Energy, and Water nexus between 2024-2050, as shown in the Table 02 starting with an analysis of electricity generation and demand future pathways, then the implementation of solar and wind energies with a capacity of 15 GW by 2035. In the other part we have assessed agricultural expansion for wheat and barley self-sufficiency by 2030. The water scenario mainly explores the Water desalination expansion to satisfy 60% of drinking water by 2030.

Table 1: Relevant data selection Sources.	
Data Type	Source
<i>Energy Demand</i>	<i>National Energy Balance; Ministry of Energy International Energy Agency</i>
<i>Energy Power Plant and Energy Infrastructure</i>	<i>Climate Compatible Growth Global Energy Monitor Ministry Of Energy, Mines and Renewable Energies SONATRACH SONELGAZ IRENA</i>
<i>Algeria National Renewable Energy Program</i>	<i>CEREFÉ ; CDER ; Groupe de la Banque africaine de développement ;</i>
<i>Agriculture Land Use and Crops production and livestock</i>	<i>Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Fishing; Food and Agriculture Organisation;</i>
<i>Food Balance</i>	<i>Food and Agriculture Organisation</i>
<i>Water and water desalination capacities and Plans</i>	<i>Food and Agriculture Organisation – AQUASTAT</i>

The emissions have been considered as a proxy for the out-interaction of these systems with the climate one. Several scenarios have been assessed, including a baseline (BAU), and renewable deployment plan, a food sovereignty scenario with 100% local wheat production, and a water desalination adaptation scenario trade-offs and policy options for sustainable development. Therefore, a relevant data must be collected from different sources as the Table 1 shows, the following diagram illustrates the reference CLEW

system for Algeria presents the interconnected flows in Algeria's Climate, Land, Energy, and Water with a particular focus on resource use, conversion processes, and sectoral demands.

Diagram 1: interconnected flows in Algeria's CLEWs system

3. Results:

The following section presents the results obtained from the integrated CLEW model, where we will highlight the key outcomes across systems under different development Scenarios, the comparison is made between the base line and alternative scenarios. We will start with Energy, then we will move to Land-Us, Water, Systems Interlinkages, at the end we will close with Emissions as a Systems-Output proxy interaction with the Climate system.

Figure 1a

Figure 1b

Figure 1c

Figure 1d

Figure 1: Electricity Generation Sources by Scenario.

The Figure 1, Shows a comparison between the electricity generation sources for different scenarios, where Algeria's electricity generation is expected to remain dependent on natural gas, regardless the electricity growth rate is. Figure 1c (bottom-left) highlights that in high-demand scenarios nuclear energy appears as a source for electricity generation to ensure stable supply.

Figure 2: The Energy Mix by scenario

Even with the implementation of the national program adding 15 GW of solar and wind by 2035, renewables would contribute only with less than 5% to the energy mix in 2050 for the 3% future demand path annual growth as shown in the Figure 2 (bottom-right). Yet the implementation of 15 GW by 2035, will preserve a approximately 2236.9 PJ of natural gas, equivalent to three years' worth of electricity generation under the Base line scenario as illustrated in Figure 3(bottom-right).

Figure 3: Natural Gas Usage for Electricity Generation Baseline Vs NERP 2035.

The ambitious goal of fully meet domestically wheat and barley consumption, this self-sufficient plan requires a significant expansion of cultivable land, around 50 000 km² by 2030 and the double by 2050, as highlighted in Figure 4a.

Figure 4c

Figure 4: Agri-land Repartition for both scenarios, baseline and 100% locally satisfied Wheat demand.

The Figure 4c (right-side) shows a noticeable decrease in crops imports, indicating a switch towards a domestic self-reliance in crops production, in the observed results a portion of irrigated land for producing crops shifted to rainfed agriculture (Figure 4b),

Figure 5: Water Precipitation use by land

forcing the system towards self-sufficient crops production will shows an increase in precipitation allocated cropland under the limits of irrigation capacities (Figure 5).

Figure 6a

Figure 6b

Figure 6: Land and Energy Inter-linkage

The land -Energy interlinks have been summed up in the Figure 6, which displays that the Land allocated to the energy system (Figure 6a) is primarily influenced by future electricity demand levels and the generation mix scenarios with higher shares of wind and solar energy require significantly more land area compared to those dominated by nuclear or natural gas.

Figure 7a

Figure 7b

Figure 7: Emissions and Costs for All Scenarios

The Figure 6b presents the energy usage for crops production, for both scenarios, where the Figure illustrates a 20 PJ of energy required by 2035 and 28 PJ by 2050 to satisfy 100% of crops demand locally. The Figure 7 illustrated the Co₂ emissions and the total costs for different scenarios, where all the scenarios are scenarios are above the Baseline, only The NERP15GW scenario consistently shows the lowest emissions as shown in Figure 7a.

4. Discussion:

The Algerian Land-Scape is a crucial in determining the climate policies and develop a sustainable strategy. The interaction between CLEW systems significantly draws the pathway lines in matter of tard-offs and different policy choices. As a major natural gas producer with immense solar energy potential, Algeria stands in between maintaining its fossil fuel-based economy of engaging in diversified future. However, constraints such water stress, limited rainfed Agricultural land, besides hight dependency on food imports especially wheat, pose a serious challenge for Algeria long-term development.

The Algeria natural gas plays pivotal role for the energy security and covering the local energy demand in one hand, while also serving as a strategic asset in the international gas market in the other hand, as the country's primary export commodity, it remains a key driver of national economic development.

The limited availability of arable land, combined with growing pressure on water resources due to the population growth, hight temperatures and low precipitation, creates significant constraints for agricultural expansion and food security. While efforts to achieve 100% of crop production is important for resilience, they must be balanced against the realities of low rainfall, declining water availability, and increasing climate variability. With nearly half of Algeria's freshwater supply coming from desalination and a majority of agricultural land depending on rainfed conditions, the country faces mounting risks linked to resource scarcity. This highlights the urgent need for integrated land and water policies, focused on improving productivity, enhancing water-use efficiency, and reducing climate vulnerability, in order to support sustainable development and national food security.

5. Conclusion:

Algeria's future development scenarios indicate a continued dependence on natural gas, with only limited progress toward renewable energy and sustainable agriculture. While the implementation of a 15 GW plan of renewables, mainly solar, will reduce emissions and water consumption, its effect on the overall energy mix remains modest in the absence of broader structural reforms. Pursuing full crop self-sufficiency enhances resilience and food sovereignty but entails significant economic and resource demands.

A coordinated and balanced strategy across the energy, land, and water sectors is crucial to ensuring long-term sustainability. Building on the results and insights from the integrated CLEWs modelling, we will outline the following key policy recommendations aiming to enhance the long-range sustainable development and resilience:

- 1- Promote the integration of Renewable energy (Solar and Wind) to lower CO₂ emissions, and minimize water consumption in electricity generation;
- 2- Smart Irrigation and Water reuse strategies to support the full Crops self-sufficiency Strategy;
- 3- Improve crop yields with prioritizing Hight-yield and climate variability resistance wheat;

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